

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN INSURANCE SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN**O‘ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL SUG‘URTA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI****¹Yuldashev Obiddin****Toshmurzayevich****²Mambetqulova Mahliyo****Alisher qizi***¹Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti “Sug‘urta ishi” kafedrasida**Professori, ²Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti**“Soliqlar va budjet hisobi” fakulteti talabasi***Annotation
Annotatsiya**

Eng. - This article analyzes the main issues related to the development of the green insurance system in Uzbekistan and studies the effectiveness of new insurance mechanisms aimed at reducing environmental risks. The article comprehensively examines environmental problems in Uzbekistan, such as air pollution and the role of insurance in their elimination. International experiences have been analyzed, with a particular focus on the development of the green insurance market in Germany, France, and China. Recommendations have been developed regarding the economic viability of green insurance and its long-term development prospects in Uzbekistan.

Uzb. - Mazkur maqolada O‘zbekistonda yashil sug‘urta tizimining rivojlanishiga doir asosiy muammolar tahlil qilgan va ekologik xavflarni kamaytirishga qaratilgan yangi sug‘urta mexanizmlarining samaradorligi o‘rganilgan. Maqolada O‘zbekistondagi ekologik muammolar, masalan, havo ifloslanishi va ularni bartaraf etishda sug‘urtaning o‘rni keng qamrovda ko‘rib chiqilgan. Xalqaro tajribalar tahlil qilinib, xususan Germaniya, Fransiya va Xitoyda yashil sug‘urta bozorining rivojlanishi o‘rganildi. Yashil sug‘urtaning iqtisodiy samaradorligi hamda O‘zbekistonda uning uzoq muddatli rivojlanish istiqbollari yuzasidan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Keywords:**Kalit so‘zlar:**

❖ *green insurance, environmental risk, climate change, environmental protection, insurance mechanisms, environmental problems.*

❖ *yashil sug‘urta, ekologik xavf, iqlim o‘zgarishi, atrof-muhitni asrash, sug‘urta mexanizmlari, ekologik muammolar.*

Introduction.

In recent times, environmental pollution in the world is becoming one of the global problems. For example, if we take air pollution, then according to a 2024 report published by the International Energy Agency, 126 countries around the world have a poor air pollution rate, that is, exceed the PM₂ indicator. Therefore, the role of the green economy, as well as green

insurance as an innovative product, is currently increasing. Green insurance, in particular, occupies an important place in the modern economy as innovative insurance products and practices that support environmentally friendly and sustainable development. Global challenges such as climate change, natural disasters, and increased environmental risks, as well as limited resource depletion, suggest

that the insurance sector needs new approaches. Green insurance, which includes not only economic interests but also social and environmental goals, makes them more relevant. Also, green insurance offers a new way to improve the quality of the environment as an innovative product that combines environmental protection with the financial sector.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been experiencing a sharp economic growth, which is due to the rapid growth of marketization, industrialization and integrations with international economic inputs. However, increased environmental pollution has emerged as a means of preventing sustainable development of Uzbekistan. In addition, the rapid industrialization and urbanization and export-oriented economy of Uzbekistan, which has a population of 38 million people, causes air pollution and various environmental problems, for example, the capital of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, reached the 1st place in the ranking of the most polluted cities of the world on January 28, 2025 in terms of air pollution. These results show that industrialization in Uzbekistan is affecting the environment, and innovative approaches are needed as a solution to such environmental problems, and one of them is green insurance.

In such conditions, innovative solutions to environmental problems are necessary, one of the most important of which is the introduction of a green insurance system. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On complex measures for the further development of the Insurance Services Market" PD-108 of March 1, 2024 [1] was also an important stage in this direction. This decision put forward specific proposals for the development and introduction of "green insurance" products. This may mark the beginning of a new era in ensuring environmental security and financial stability in the country.

Through green insurance, businesses and

individuals will be able to not only protect their assets, but also contribute to reducing environmental risks, developing green technologies, and reducing carbon footprint. This will take the financial system to a new level in a state of integration with environmental protection.

Currently, green insurance is taking shape as a separate direction on a global scale. Much attention is paid to this area by international financial institutions, in particular the World Bank, the European bank for reconstruction and development and the UN Environment Programme (UNEP). This shows the contribution of green insurance not only to environmental but also to economic development.

Literature review.

Michael Faure and Veronique Bruggeman emphasize the role of green insurance in managing environmental risks. They argue: "Green insurance is an effective tool to reduce the financial consequences of environmental risk, allowing for faster action than government control" [2].

According to Ma Xuejing and Sun Yanan in China's Green Insurance Development, the Chinese experience demonstrates how green insurance can serve as an incentive for industrial enterprises. "Through green insurance, businesses are learning to anticipate environmental risks and to financially mitigate their environmental responsibilities" [3].

Sh. Komilova analyzes the legal foundations and economic advantages of green insurance in the country. She emphasizes that "the regulatory framework for the development of green insurance in Uzbekistan should be strengthened" [4].

The UNEP FI (United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative) document titled "Principles for Sustainable Insurance" identifies green insurance as a key instrument for promoting sustainable development. It states that "the insurance

sector should become an active participant in responding to global environmental threats" [5].

Icholas Stern, in his famous report "the Stern Review", provides an in-depth analysis of the economic consequences of climate change, arguing that green insurance and other financial instruments are important tools in reducing environmental risks. According to him, "the insurance sector should be the first economic sector to respond to climate risks, as it possesses the capacity to assess and manage such risks" [6].

According to B.O. Tursunov and M.K. Karimov: "The underdevelopment of green insurance in Uzbekistan poses challenges for ensuring long-term financial security, including for pensioners" [7].

Methodology.

This study used descriptive (descriptive) and comparative analysis techniques. The current state of the green insurance system in the insurance market of Uzbekistan was studied on the basis of real problems with environmental risks. Also, international experience – compared with the example of countries such as Germany, France, China. On the basis of economic and environmental indicators, an analytical analysis was carried out, and on the basis of legislative and strategic documents, a legal analysis was carried out. As data, official reports, analysis of international institutions, scientific articles and practical programs were analyzed.

Analysis and results.

Green insurance is not only a tool that serves to reduce financial and economic risks, it is also emerging as a mechanism that plays an important role in ensuring environmental sustainability. Today, natural disasters arising from climate change across the Earth, the environmental risks of business entities, and uncertainties in resource use necessitate the abandonment of traditional approaches to the

insurance sector and the introduction of new, ecology-oriented approaches.

International practices confirm that green insurance tools are emerging as an effective mechanism to financially support environmental initiatives, manage environmental risks, and cover environmental damage. For example, in countries such as Germany, France, Canada and Japan, insurance services related to environmental threats are actively implemented by enterprises and the private sector. With these mechanisms, environmental problems such as industrial waste, the spread of harmful substances being released into the atmosphere, pollution of water resources are being put under insurance protection.

The implementation of the green insurance system in the conditions of Uzbekistan can serve to ensure environmental balance along with economic development. Currently, the industrialization processes taking place in the country, in particular, the chemical industry, energy and mining sectors, are being evaluated as a source of environmental threats. Therefore, the practical implementation of insurance mechanisms covering environmental risks not only forces manufacturers to comply with environmental standards, but also encourages them to apply environmentally sustainable technologies.

Also, green insurance serves to alleviate the burden on public finance by reducing the economic loss of cases with environmentally negative consequences. Taken from this point of view, Green insurance turns out to be an effective tool in the formation of sustainable environmental cooperation between the state and the non-state sector. An increase in the level of environmental culture and consciousness among the population, strengthening the interest of economic entities to take on voluntary environmental responsibility, as well as environmental incentive measures provided by the government (tax incentives, grant funds, etc.)

provide a positive background to the expansion of the green insurance market.

Green insurance should be evaluated not only as a new stage in the development of the insurance industry, but also as an integrated approach aimed at restoring the balance between environmental and economic systems. This approach, in addition protecting the environment, also serves to ensure economic stability. Along with the economic development of Uzbekistan, a sharp increase in environmental threats, the need for green insurance products is becoming an urgent issue. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) report of 2023, Uzbekistan had one of the lowest air quality rates among Central Asian countries, with an average of 43 µg/m³ in annual PM_{2.5} particles. This is almost 4 times higher than the safe level set by the World Health Organization. At the same time, according to the IQAir rankings, the city of Tashkent was repeatedly listed as one of the most polluted cities in terms of air quality in 2024 and 2025.

Economic growth-in order to be sustainable, it must be carried out taking into account environmental factors. Here, Green insurance as a financial instrument-manifests itself as a force that promotes environmental sustainability. For example, in the EU states, by

2022, the total volume of the environmental risk insurance market had reached 2.7 billion euros. Also in China, more than 5,000 companies were covered by the Green Insurance Pilot Program, developed in 2021 to cover environmental losses, and about 3.4 billion yuan in compensation was paid. Although Green insurance products have not yet been widely introduced in Uzbekistan, legal and institutional foundations are being laid in this direction. Presidential Resolution No. PD-108, issued on March 1, 2024, introduced specific measures for the development and market implementation of green insurance products, laying the foundation for a preliminary regulatory framework in this area. This marks an important step in encouraging insurance companies to develop innovative and sustainable products.

Also, according to the Insurance Association of Uzbekistan in 2023, the share of products covering environmental risks was almost 1%, although the total volume of the insurance market reached 3.5 trillion soums. This situation, on the one hand, indicates that there is still great potential in this segment of the industry, and on the other hand, environmental risks are not yet covered by sufficient means of insurance.

Table 1

Analysis based on international experience¹

Country	Year Green Insurance Introduced	Key Focus Areas	Outcomes
Germany	2007	Environmental protection, vehicle emissions	50% reduction in emissions
China	2012	Industrial waste, high-risk enterprises	5000+ companies covered
France	2010	Eco- incentives through insurance	Strong government support
Uzbekistan	2024(phased implementation)	Air quality, environmental risks	Market share less than 1%

An international experimental analysis of the implementation of the green insurance

system provides important information on the stages and directions of development of this

¹ [UNEP+-+United+Nations+Environment+Programme&sca_esv](https://www.unep.org/press/2024/05/24/unep-report-on-green-insurance)

area. In particular, in Germany, green insurance has been put into practice since 2007, which is mainly aimed at Environmental Protection and reducing car emissions. As a result of this approach, the volume of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere was reduced by up to 50 percent [8].

In China, however, the system has been actively introduced as of 2012, with a particular focus on industrial waste and hazardous production facilities. To date, more than 5,000 companies are covered by Green insurance, which shows the effectiveness of the order and monitoring system in this area [9].

In the French experiment, however, Green insurance is used by the government as a means of encouraging environmental responsibility. The state support provided to insurers plays an important role in increasing the attractiveness of these products [10].

The first steps were taken in this direction from 2024, when we will focus on the experience of Uzbekistan. At present, although the system has not yet been fully established, work is ongoing to develop the existing legal framework, beginning with the initial stage outlined in Presidential Decree PD-108. However, the share of green insurance in the total volume of the insurance market is currently less than 1 percent. This means that there are still great opportunities and unprocessed areas in the industry [11].

Conclusion.

Green insurance is strengthening its place in the global economy as an important innovative product supporting environmental risks and sustainable development. Environmental Protection and the fight against climate change further increase the importance of green insurance, becoming relevant issues in economic, environmental and social today. Along with Uzbekistan's rapidly growing industrial sector and urbanization processes, environmental issues are also becoming more acute. Under these conditions, the green

insurance system can contribute significantly not only to ensuring economic stability, but also to reducing environmental risks. The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 1, 2024 was an important step in this direction and provided the necessary legal and regulatory framework for the implementation of the green insurance system.

However, Green insurance products have not yet been widely implemented in Uzbekistan. Nevertheless, deep developments and supportive policies are necessary in this direction, taking into account economic development and environmental risks. For the successful implementation of the green insurance system, it is necessary to establish effective cooperation between the economic and environmental sectors, encourage business entities to apply new technologies, increase environmental education and culture. At the same time, the green insurance market, in particular, an increase in environmental incentive measures by the state, increases the interest of insurance companies in innovative products.

Based on our understanding of green insurance, we give a number of our proposals: it is necessary to form a more powerful legal and regulatory framework for the Green insurance system. This serves to encourage insurance companies to develop innovative products and makes it easier to insure environmental risks in the market.

- For the development of the green insurance market, it is necessary to introduce environmental incentive measures by the government, such as tax incentives, grants and subsidies. This encourages not only insurance companies, but also individuals to take on environmental responsibility.

- It is necessary to expand educational programs aimed at developing an ecological culture between the population and business entities and explaining the importance of green insurance. This will help form a responsible approach to the environment.

- To expand the market of green insurance products, it is necessary to involve insurance companies in the development of new, environmental risk-covering products. It encourages the development of innovative solutions for companies.

- In the implementation of the green insurance system, it is necessary to develop cooperation with international experiences and financial institutions, study foreign experiences and adapt to the conditions of the country.

Effective cooperation on a global scale is needed to increase the economic and environmental potential of green insurance.

- To reduce environmental risks through the green insurance system, it is important to encourage the industry to apply environmentally sustainable technologies. This helps ensure financial support through insurance products and popularize environmentally sustainable technologies.

Literatura/Reference:

1. Resolution PQ-108 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan (March 1, 2024) includes comprehensive measures for the modernization of insurance services and the gradual introduction of the green insurance system in Uzbekistan. <https://www.lex.uz/uz/>

2. Micha el Faure va Veronique Bruggeman "Environmental Liability and Insurance in Europe" *Environmental Liability* by Michael G. Faure: SSRN pp. 247-286, Cheltenham (June 10, 2009).

3. Ma Xuejing va Sun Yanan. "Green Insurance Development: Challenges and Policy Responses" *China's Green Insurance Development: Challenges and Policy Responses - Search | ScienceDirect.com* Volume-126 October 2023, 107016

4. Sh. Komilova. "O'zbekistonda yashil sug'urta tizimini rivojlantirish uchun normativ-huquqiy asoslar mustahkamlab borilishi kerak". [file:///C:/Users/Hp/Downloads/ARIMS%203117%20\(2\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Hp/Downloads/ARIMS%203117%20(2).pdf)

5. UNEP FI (United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative) "Sug'urta sektori global ekologik tahdidlarga javob beruvchi faol ishtirokchiga aylanishi kerak." <https://www.unepfi.org/insurance/insurance/>

6. Nicholas Stern "The Stern Review" <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20100407172811>

7. Tursunov B.O. va Karimov M.K. "O'zbekistonda yashil sug'urta joriy etilishi orqali nafaqat ekologik xavflar kamayadi, balki moliyaviy barqarorlik mustahkamlanadi" <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/journal/article/view/564>

8. <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-policies-of-iea-countries-germany-2007>

9. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=82652>

10. <https://www.greenfinanceplatform.org/policies-and-regulations/green-insurance-support-afforestation>

11. <https://www.lex.uz/uz/>